

7. NG. PH. BUU-HOI and P. JACQUINGTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4173.
8. J. H. WILKINSON and I. L. FINAR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 759, 1948, 288.
9. R. M. BRADLOW and C. A. VANDERWERF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 654.
10. *Organic Syntheses, Vol. 3*, p. 53, John Wiley and Sons, Inc. N. Y. 1955.
11. M. L. TAMAYO, G. ALONSO and R. MADRERO, *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, 57, 9834 d.
12. U.S.D.A., *Circular No. 198*, 1931.

**Chemical Constituents of *Gmelina philippensis*,
Adenocalymna nitida, *Allamanda cathartica*,
Averrhoa carambola and *Maba buxifolia***

K. P. TIWARI, M. MASOOD and P. K. MINOCHA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad

*Manuscript received 7 July 1978, revised 16 March 1979,
accepted 4 August 1979*

GMELINA *philippensis* (N. O. Verbenaceae), *Adenocalymna nitida* (N. O. Bignoniaceae), *Allamanda cathartica* (N. O. Apocyanaceae) and *Averrhoa carambola* (N. O. Oxalidaceae) are very often cultivated in Indian gardens. Some of them find extensive medicinal uses for the treatment of various ailments^{1,2}. The presence of kaempferol and quercetin from the flowers of *A. cathartica* has already been reported³.

The air dried flowers (1 kg each) of *G. philippensis*, *A. nitida*, *A. cathartica* and *A. carambola* were extracted exhaustively with ethanol separately. The ethanolic extracts were concentrated and they were extracted with petroleum ether to remove oil and fats. The concentrated extracts left after the extraction with petroleum ether were extracted with acetone. The acetone extracts were concentrated and adsorbed onto the column of magnesol⁴. On eluting with ethyl acetate saturated with water kaempferol, C₁₅H₁₀O₆, m.p. 276-8°(d) has been obtained from *G. philippensis*, *A. nitida* and *A. cathartica*, quercetin, C₁₅H₁₀O₇, m.p. 316°(d) and hesperitin C₁₆H₁₀O₈, m.p. 220-2°(d) were obtained from *A. nitida* and *A. cathartica* and quercetin-3-O-β-D-glucoside, C₂₁H₂₀O₁₂, m.p. 234-6° and rutin, C₂₇H₃₀O₁₆, m.p. 188° were obtained from *A. carambola*. The glycosides were characterised by the spectral studies and studies of their hydrolysis products.

Previous studies have shown the presence of 7, 9, 9 trimethyl hexa cosan-8 one, friedelin, friedelin-3-ol, oleanolic acid, quercetin, taxifolin and taxifolin-7-O-α-L galactopyranoside from the stem of *M. buxifolia*⁵.

The air dried, powdered and defatted leaves (3 kg) of *M. buxifolia* were extracted exhaustively with ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated to a thick viscous mass. The thick viscous mass

was taken in water (1 litre) and was shaken vigorously. The water insoluble substances were separated by filtration. The filtrate on concentration gave a thick brown syrupy substance which was found to be flavonoid glycoside. The study of syrupy flavonoid glycoside is in progress.

The water insoluble fraction was extracted exhaustively with hexane to remove chlorophyll and fat. The water insoluble fraction, left after the removal of chlorophyll and fat was extracted with chloroform (4 × 100 ml). The chloroform insoluble substance was recrystallised from hot ethanol, m.p. 102° which could not be studied due to paucity of the material. The chloroform extract was concentrated and passed through a column of silica gel using mixture of benzene and chloroform (1 : 1) as solvent whereupon friedelin, C₃₀H₅₀O, m.p. 265° and friedelin-3-ol C₃₀H₅₂O, m.p. 281-2° were obtained.

Acknowledgement

The authors are very grateful to Drs. D. S. Bhakuni (CDRI, Lucknow), T. R. Govindachari, R. S. Grewal, S. Selvavinayakam (CIBA-GEIGY Research Centre, Bombay) for providing spectral data of the compounds reported in this paper.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, 'Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants', C.S.I.B., New Delhi Publication, 1956, p. 11 and 81.
2. L. H. BAILLY, *The Standard Cyclopedia of Horticulture*, Macmillan Co., New York, Vol. I, 215.
3. S. SANKARA SUBRAMANIAN and M. M. SWAMY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1963, 32, 308.
4. C. H. ICE and S. H. WENDER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, 240, 1616.
5. Y. K. S. RATHORE, D. Phil. Thesis, University of Allahabad, 1977.

The Correlation between Carbonyl Stretching Frequencies, Force Constant and Formal Bond Order in Carbonyl Complexes

K. GOSWAMI and M. M. SINGH*

Department of Chemistry, Dibrugarh University
Dibrugarh 786 004, Assam

Manuscript received 4 August 1978, accepted 13 July 1979

A large number of carbonyl complexes of transition metals have been prepared and studied. Of all the physical methods of their investigations, the use of i.r. method with special reference to carbonyl bands is the most informative. The shifts of carbonyl stretching frequencies and their intensities have been explained on the basis of involvement of metal d_π or p_z orbitals in π-bonding with CO and

other ligands present. These shifts actually reflect the change in CO bond order 'n' which is obviously related to force constant k_{CO} . In fact Cotton and Kraihanzel have developed a quantitative relationship between k_{CO} and 'n' on the basis of simpler vibrational analysis^{1,2}. We are reporting here a very simple but useful empirical relationship between ν_{CO} and 'n' which enables one to calculate formal CO force constants.

In Table 1 the ν_{CO} values and force constant data for CO group in rhodium, iridium and few other metal complexes have been given. The k_{CO} values are calculated by using the ν_{CO} values of respective compounds. The force constant values thus obtained are only relative or 'formal' in the sense that their changes in a series of compounds qualitatively express the influence of other ligands present. Our values of force constants are therefore only qualitative in these complexes. The main aim to have relative or formal 'k' values is to see if some relationship exists between k_{CO} and 'n' of the CO group. In order to find the bond order of carbonyl groups in the complexes we have used the following procedure. By anchoring the ν_{CO} -n plot (Figure 1) on the reference species of pure CO having $\nu_{CO}=2143\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (bond order 3) and ketonic CO having $\nu_{CO}=1730\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (bond order 2) which are conventionally accepted values, it is possible at least qualitatively to estimate the CO bond order within reasonable limits of error for the series of carbonyl compounds. The plot can be used to get 'n' in many carbonyl complexes. These n values obtained from the plot have also been quoted in the Table 1 in which other related data ν_{CO} and k_{CO} are included. Now the empirical relationship which holds good for direct evaluation of bond order for mono-carbonyl complexes is found to be $\nu_{CO}=413n+904$. This correlation though qualitative and approximate in nature is expected to be useful even in those cases

TABLE 1—THE VALUES OF ν_{CO} (IN cm^{-1}), k_{CO} ($\text{mdyne}/\text{A}^\circ$) AND 'n' FOR CARBONYL COMPLEXES

Compounds	ν_{CO}	k_{CO}	n
	(in cm^{-1})	$\text{mdyne}/\text{A}^\circ$	
1. Cr(CO) ₆	2000	16.16	2.65
2. Mo(CO) ₆	2004	16.22	2.67
3. W(CO) ₆	1984	15.9	2.62
4. Ni(CO) ₄	2043	16.86	2.76
5. [Pt(CO)Cl ₃] ⁻	2106	17.91	2.92
6. cis Pt(CO)Cl ₂ (PEt ₃)	2100	17.81	2.89
7. trans Pt(CO)Cl(PPh ₃) ₂	2120	18.15	2.94
8. RhH(CO)(PPh ₃) ₃	1926	14.98	2.48
9. Rh(CO) × (Phen) [*]	1940	15.20	2.51
10. Rh(CO)E(AsPh ₃) ₃	1955	15.44	2.54
11. Rh(CO)Cl(AsPh ₃) ₂	1966	15.61	2.58
12. Rh(CO)CN(AsPh ₃) ₂	1990	15.99	2.62
13. Rh(CO)Cl(AsPh ₃) ₂ (SO ₂)	2030	16.64	2.74
14. Rh(CO)Cl(AsPh ₃) ₂ (TCNE) ^{**}	2070	17.31	2.82
15. Rh(CO)Cl ₂ (AsPh ₃) ₂	2110	17.98	2.92
16. IrH(CO)(PPh ₃) ₃	1930	15.04	2.49
17. Ir(CO)Cl(PPh ₃) ₃	1950	15.36	2.54
18. Ir(CO)Cl(PPh ₃) ₂ (H ₂)	1975	15.75	2.59
19. Ir(CO)Cl(PPh ₃) ₂ (O ₂)	2000	16.16	2.65
20. Ir(CO)Cl(PPh ₃) ₂ H ₂ O	2025	16.56	2.72
21. Ir(CO)Cl ₂ (PPh ₃) ₂	2080	17.47	2.85
22. OsBr ₂ (CO)(PPh ₃) ₃	1920	14.88	2.46
23. RuBr ₂ (CO)(PPh ₃) ₃	1922	14.92	2.47

* Phen - o-phenanthroline.

** TCNE - tetracyanoethylene.

where rigorous mathematical calculations and complex vibrational analysis are required. In case of metal carbonyls Cotton in collaboration with Kraihanzel^{1,2} have convincingly established a linear relationship between formal CO force constant and formal bond order n and that within the interval of $3.0 \geq n \geq 1.5$, $\Delta k/\Delta n = 6.8\text{ mdyne}/\text{A}^\circ$ per unit bond order change. The k and n values obtained from the empirical relationship or from the plot (Figure 1) are in good agreement with those calculated by using the relationship between k and n suggested by Cotton and Kraihanzel. This is demonstrated by the data of Δk and Δn given in the Table 2. Cotton

TABLE 2—VALUES OF Δk AND Δn OF THE COMPOUNDS AS NUMBERED ON TABLE 1

Compounds	Δk	Δn	$\Delta k/\Delta n$
15-8	8	0.44	6.8
15-9	2.78	0.41	6.78
15-10	2.55	0.37	6.89
15-11	2.37	0.34	6.97
15-12	1.99	0.29	6.86
15-13	1.33	0.19	7.0
15-14	0.67	0.1	6.7
21-16	2.43	0.36	6.75
21-17	2.11	0.32	6.6
21-18	1.72	0.26	6.6
21-19	1.31	0.19	6.8
21-20	0.92	0.13	7.0
21-8	2.49	0.37	6.73
1-22	1.28	0.19	6.74
2-23	1.30	0.2	6.5

and Wilkinson³ assigned bond orders for the compounds $\text{Cr}(\text{CO})_6$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_4$ as 2.65 and 2.75 respectively which are almost similar to the data calculated from the above relationship. Thus it appears that the empirical relationship given above can be used to get the formal bond order in carbonyl compounds having single carbonyl bands with fair degree of precision without recourse to rigorous mathematical calculations.

References

1. C. S. KRAIHAENZEL and F. A. COTTON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 533.
2. F. A. COTTON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 702.
3. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, *Advanced Inorganic Chemistry*, Interscience, 3rd. Edition, 1972, p. 699.